

APPLICATIONS OF COMPOSITES IN THE U.S. NAVY

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The U.S. Navy composite materials research and development program is aimed at improving the scientific and technological base needed for application of composites to future naval systems. The program is both materials and structures oriented and covers fiber-reinforced organic-matrix composites and fiber-reinforced and in situ metal-matrix composites. This paper describes some selected present and future naval applications of composite materials, recent progress in associated research and development programs, and some composite systems currently under examination.

Introduction

The U.S. Navy is committed to the use of composites in structural applications and accordingly has a broad research and development program directed toward this end. The program is divided for administrative purposes into materials and structures, this organization evolving during a period in which isotropic materials were the primary interest. Now the demarcation between materials and structures is diminishing as it is becoming more clearly recognized that for meaningful evaluation of materials in structural applications the actual end use conditions should be simulated as closely as possible. It is generally recognized that mechanical properties measured at room temperature may not reflect behavior at elevated temperatures, and tests in a dry environment may not reflect behavior in a humid environment. However, it is often not recognized that results from constant amplitude fatigue tests may not represent those under spectrum loading. In addition, in the case of orthotropic materials, uniaxial loading tests may not accurately characterize behavior under conditions of biaxial or in-plane loading often encountered in structures. Also data obtained on unidirectional composites do not adequately reflect the behavior of multidirectional composites.

Thus, in the course of evaluating materials for an application, it is important to address the structural end item in its composition and loading. Analytical techniques have been developed and are being developed to permit the extrapolation of relatively simple data for calculating responses to more complex situations. However, analytical capabilities are limited and it is necessary to resort to experimentation for most types of mechanical characterization. In addition, from the materials standpoint, it is extremely important to fully characterize the composites being evaluated. Curing conditions, void content, fiber content, fiber finish, matrix composition and the defect structure are factors that affect composite materials behavior and should be known for any mechanical characterization program.

Finally, for a given reinforcement and matrix, an infinite number of composites can be produced. One can vary the reinforcement--matrix ratio, the direction of the reinforcement in each ply, the stacking sequence of the various plies and the conditions of fabrication. In addition, several reinforcements can be used together to form a single composite material. The various mechanical properties are changed by each of these modifications.

The foregoing is illustrative of the fact that the evaluation of composite materials for use in structures is in its infancy. More sophisticated concepts for properties determination and design techniques will have to be developed to obtain optimum utilization of these materials, and undoubtedly computer technology will be

called upon to treat the many complexities involved.

The current U.S. Navy's materials program on composites is based on (1) anticipating materials requirements for future systems and supporting development of the scientific and technological base required for these materials; (2) generating the information needed for understanding composite materials behavior with the aim of characterizing and improving their properties and performance. The structures program complements this by developing the technology required for composite materials to be applied confidently in the quest for improved structural performance, increased reliability, reduced vulnerability and reduced life cycle costs. Especially important in the course of this overall effort is the desired, strong interplay and high degree of coordination that occurs between the materials and structures programs.

Organic-Matrix Composites

Applications

The U.S. Navy uses composite materials in numerous structural applications. Possibly the Navy's major accomplishment to date in the field of composites is the fiberglass-epoxy Polaris missile chamber, the first major filament-wound primary structure. This program advanced the entire field of filament winding generating information on design, materials, fabrication and quality assurance, and transformed a laboratory technique into a production process for primary structures used in commercial as well as military components.

The first filament-wound Polaris chambers used E-glass fiber reinforcement with epoxy resin resulting in both weight savings and increased reliability compared to the previous steel chambers. Later the E-glass was replaced by S-glass possessing an improved epoxy-compatible finish; this permitted an increased design stress. As the filament winding technology improved, the design stress increased further. Now Kevlar is replacing fiberglass in the Trident missile program, and the reason for this is apparent from Table I. The single fiber strengths shown in the first column must be reduced due to the variability observed in the materials as reflected in the minimum strength values listed. Kevlar has a higher specific strength than the other candidate fibers and adequate stiffness. While Kevlar is more expensive than glass, it is nevertheless considered to be cost effective.

Kevlar is not without its problems, however; there appears to be poor bonding between the Kevlar fibers and epoxy resin. Obviously, the fiber chemical surface finish is not yet optimized. This creates a possibility for degrading moisture effects on strength. Furthermore, Kevlar composites have poor interlaminar

shear strength, which affects the mode of failure and, accordingly, the design. The transverse strains must be kept low compared to fiberglass composites, for example. Care is required in fabricating with Kevlar because the fibers absorb moisture until encapsulated in resin. Nevertheless, the composite properties make this material sufficiently attractive to warrant taking the steps to circumvent these problems.

Another major application of composites in the U.S. Navy is in utility, personnel and motor whale boats up to 15 meters in length. The boats are made of glass woven roving and fire-retardant polyester resin and their use dates back twenty-five years with thousands now in service. The composite boats are less expensive than aluminum boats of the same size.

An interesting recent application is the fairing for the Deep Submergence Rescue Vehicle which consists of three metal spheres joined together in a row. The fairing is approximately 12 1/2 meters long and 2 1/2 meters in diameter with a wall thickness of approximately 0.6 cm. It was fabricated from glass cloth and epoxy using a vacuum bag - autoclave process and weighs approximately two tons. The fairing is free flooding and need not withstand the pressures to which the vehicle itself is exposed.

There are many other naval applications of composites. These include aircraft and ship radomes made from glass fibers and polyester or epoxy resins, submarine sonar domes, submarine fairwaters and superstructures, ship masts, handrails, stanchions, ladders, liquid storage tanks, ventilation ducts, deckhouses and piping. In addition to these current applications there is a well-planned research and development program to evaluate and improve composite materials for new applications. Some interesting projects in this program will be discussed in the remaining sections of the paper.

Materials Program

(a) Phthalocyanine Resins. New heat resistant resins are being developed from the phthalocyanine family formed by stereochemical arrangement of four reacting phthalonitrile groups, such as

They are synthesized from 4-aminophthalonitrile and diacid chlorides. The resins pass through the liquid state on curing and cure without the elimination of small gaseous molecules. They can be cured by heat alone and the cured resins are thermally stable above 200°C. There is no loss in weight when the resins are heated in air at 215°C up to 570 hours, but there is a gradual loss in weight at 275°C. The limiting factor in their thermal stability appears to be the amide linkage. These resins show promise for use in composites, coatings, adhesives and plastics. They have been used to produce adhesive bonded joints having reasonable strength, and carbon fiber composites are now being made for evaluation.

(b) Thermoplastic Resin Composites. An interesting development in the field of organic-matrix composites is the use of thermoplastic resins as matrices in structural laminates. It has been assumed in the past that composites made with thermoplastic resins would have poor creep resistance and lack high temperature capability for use in structural applications. However, recent work for the Navy has shown that this assumption is not always correct. Studies have been conducted using a polysulfone resin with glass fabric. A prepreg was made from which laminate sheets were molded and compared to laminates made from a typical epoxy resin prepreg. The mechanical properties of these polysulfone laminates generally meet or exceed those of the epoxy laminates at temperatures up to 150°-175°C. The tensile strength is approximately 55,000 psi at 22°C and 40,000 psi at 150°C, which is comparable to that of several high temperature epoxy systems. The interlaminar shear strength is 7000 psi at room temperature for the polysulfone compared to 9500 psi for the epoxy, and the Izod impact strength is 15 ft-lb/in for the former compared to 11 ft-lb/in for the latter. Tensile creep studies of 50% of the ultimate stress indicate little creep in 1000 hours up to 120°C. At 175°C, the specimens fail in 100 hours. The creep is significantly less than that of the epoxy laminate. Limited fatigue tests indicate behavior similar to that of epoxy laminate. Flexural tests after a seventy-two hour water boil show 40% and 23% reductions from the original values for the polysulfone and epoxy laminates, respectively. The reduction for the polysulfone is apparently due to poor bonding between the matrix and the fiber which can be alleviated by an improved surface finish.

Limited tests have been conducted on polysulfone laminates made with surface treated, high tensile strength graphite fibers. Typical property values, presented in Table II, compare favorably with results obtained for graphite-epoxy composites. Again the Izod impact values are higher for polysulfone laminates than for epoxy. In creep rupture tests conducted at 50% and 80% of the ultimate stress, the polysulfone laminate has a slightly higher initial strain than the epoxy laminates, but both show the same trends thereafter. Limited fatigue tests on unidirectional speci-

mens indicate fatigue properties equal to or better than epoxies.

Thus the fiber reinforced polysulfone laminates exhibit mechanical properties very close to those achieved by epoxy laminates with usable properties maintained up to about 150°C. The polysulfone laminates appear to have reasonably good water resistance. However, in contrast to epoxy materials, the polysulfone prepreg has infinite storage life, and polysulfone laminates can be reformed since the matrix is thermoplastic. This opens up a broad range of fabrication techniques not previously available to thermosetting structural composites. The main drawback of these materials appears to be creep above 150 C and susceptibility to attack by some solvents. Nevertheless, the great promise that these materials hold has led to the initiation of development programs for typical aircraft components as will be discussed later.

(c) Graphite Cloth. A recent development in the field of graphite fiber technology is the use of graphite-epoxy prepreg cloth rather than tape for structural components. Unidirectional tape has been assumed to be the most strength effective form of prepreg to use. The Navy has compared test lots of a prepreg made from a fabric of approximately equal biaxial weave to a quasi-isotropic laminate made from prepreg tape. It was found that the properties of the cloth laminate are very close to those obtained from the tape laminate, Table III; however, the coefficient of variation in properties was less for the cloth laminate, so the B-basis design allowables are actually higher than for the tape laminates. In addition, the cloth is available in greater widths than the tape and is easier to handle. Even with a slightly higher materials cost, it has been calculated that the use of cloth prepreg can result in manufacturing fabrication cost reductions of 35% and more. The fabrication of complex shapes can also be simplified by the use of cloth and unbalanced weaves can be made in cloth for specific applications. This material appears to present an interesting new form for carbon fiber composites.

(d) Cavitation Erosion. One of the Navy's studies of environmental effects on composites involves cavitation erosion, which is a potential problem in hydrofoils. The erosion resistance of composite materials is being measured using the device described in standard ASTM Test Method G 32-72, "Vibratory Cavitation Erosion Test". It consists of a transducer coupled to a titanate exponential horn. When the tip of the horn is immersed in water and vibrated, cavitation occurs. Specimens are suspended 0.020 mil from the horn and erosion determined by weight loss as a function of time. The results in Figure 1 show that a titanium alloy exhibits the lowest erosion rate, while the most resistant composite material is edge-oriented, glass-fiber epoxy. Most of the other composite materials show erosion resistance superior to that of the aluminum alloy measured.

In organic-matrix composites, cavitation generally begins by cracking and eroding of the matrix material exposing the fibers which then fracture. There is some similarity between cavitation and rain erosion, but the forces involved in cavitation are much greater. Therefore, knowledge gained in rain erosion studies has limited application to the current problem. An analytical program has been initiated to parallel the experimental studies.

(e) Computer Programs. Recently a survey was made of special purpose computer programs for use in composite structure analysis. The programs fell into four categories: strength and stiffness analysis, laminate optimization and bonded-joint analysis. Most composite structure activities were research and development oriented with a few production applications starting to appear. In most cases additional development would be required to make the programs useful on a production basis.

Computer programs which have been developed for predicting the strength of laminates utilize various failure criteria, but these programs are no better than the failure criteria they use for their particular application. Attempts have been made in structural design at optimization of laminates using computer programs. Many of these programs are pseudo-optimization based on the use of 0, ± 45 , and 90 degree reinforcement orientations only. The reasoning is that sufficiently good designs can be developed using these orientations and that fabrication is greatly facilitated by limiting the lay-ups to these angles only. The previously cited limitation imposed by the accuracy of failure criteria applies to the design optimization programs as well. In addition, it does not appear that these programs take into account the inevitable presence of defects. That is probably because broad failure criteria have not been established yet for composites containing defects and flaws. This represents a practical limitation to the utility of computer programs for strength and design optimization of composite materials and bonded joints.

(f) Mechanics of Composites. Studies are underway on the mechanics of composite materials. In one project, the Navy is looking at the stress concentrations produced by broken fibers in a unidirectional composite. The assumptions are made that the fibers carry the normal load and the matrix the transverse load and shear and that the composite is subjected to uniform tensile loads along the fibers. It is found that the stress concentration is finite and increases without bound as more fibers fail. The stress concentration is slightly less than the square root of the number of fibers broken and is not sensitive to the volume fraction of fibers in the composite because displacements are a function of the longitudinal portion only.

Another project is concerned with the behavior of materials that have different moduli in tension and compression. An exact

buckling criterion, within the framework of classical buckling theory, has been derived for eccentrically stiffened multilayered circular cylindrical shells made with such materials. The material model is based on a bilinear stress-strain curve with a discontinuity in slope at the origin. The buckling criterion is found to be valid for arbitrary combinations of axial and circumferential loading, including axial compression and internal pressure as well as axial tension and lateral pressure.

Studies are in progress to derive failure functions to describe the behavior of composite materials and bonded joints using fracture mechanics concepts. The work involves the development of failure criteria such as strain energy release rate, or stress intensity factor, or another invariant parameter for composite materials. Different functions will have to be developed for different modes of defect growth, such as a through-crack and delamination.

Work on the application of fracture mechanics to bonded joints has been in progress in the Navy for a number of years with very interesting and useful results. The influence of the type of adhesive, bond thickness, temperature, crack velocity and mode of loading on bond toughness as characterized by G , strain energy release rate, has been demonstrated. This parameter is starting to be used by structures organizations in the USA, and a standard test method is being prepared in the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM). The Navy is continuing to investigate methods for increasing the toughness of adhesive bonds as demonstrated by increases in strain energy release rate for both tensile and shear loading. Other studies are directed toward interfacial cracks and the quantitative effects of surface roughness, surface treatment, residual stresses, environment, and crack velocity.

Structures Program

The Navy composite structures program is directed towards developing the technology and confidence required for these materials to be used in various Navy applications. Attention is focused mainly on graphite and boron filaments used with an epoxy matrix, in some cases in combination with glass fibers.

The Navy has a very active program investigating the use of composites in Naval aircraft, existing and proposed fixed-wing aircraft and helicopters. Many publications have detailed the potential weight-savings and cost-savings that can be realized by using composite materials in aircraft structural components. Other potential advantages include greater aircraft availability through increased fatigue life, improved battle damage tolerance, and finally, an item of critical importance to the Navy, reduced corrosion with a resultant reduction in maintenance. This is a dominating factor because of the environment in which Naval aircraft operate.

Typical examples will be cited of the Navy's program involving the use of organic-matrix composite structures in aircraft. A composite spoiler for the S-3A aircraft is being designed which should eliminate corrosion, simplify manufacturing, decrease weight and reduce costs. The metal spoiler consists of 63 detail parts. The composite spoiler has a sandwich construction with two variable thickness, graphite-epoxy face skins over a glass-reinforced plastic honeycomb core, selected primarily for corrosion resistance. Only three major parts plus two metal hinge fittings are required in the composite component. A weight savings of 26% has been achieved, and a cost savings of 20% on the first 200 units is expected. Several units have been fabricated and static and fatigue tests successfully conducted to design requirements.

An overwing fairing for the F-14 airplane is being designed to demonstrate the cost and weight savings possible with the use of hybrid composites in aircraft components representative of primary structures, and uses a combination of composite materials, graphite-epoxy, boron-epoxy, and fiberglass-epoxy, plus metals. A weight reduction of 22% has been achieved and a cost savings of 40% for 100 units is expected. Following static and fatigue tests, components will be flight tested.

Another program in progress is aimed at demonstrating the benefits of a high modulus composite, graphite-epoxy, in a helicopter rotor blade. The H-3 rotor blade will utilize both graphite and glass fiber reinforcements. It is expected to provide a 900 lb increase in lift, a 15 knot increase in speed, as well as improved fatigue life, damage tolerance and corrosion resistance. The blade will have an optimum aerodynamic configuration which can be readily fabricated using a composite material, and the higher stresses produced by this design are practicable due to the excellent fatigue properties of the composite. The initial costs should be no more than 20% over that of the current production metal blade, but both the reliability and maintenance should be improved. Blades are being fabricated for evaluation.

Most studies of composites for structural applications have involved the replacement of a metal component. Therefore the external configuration and design are set by the metals technology. The greatest benefit from the use of composites is attained by reconfiguration of the component or structure in the preliminary design stage to take full advantage of the versatility of fiber-reinforced composites. A study is therefore in progress to determine the advantages that can be realized by an original composite design of an unmanned drone. In the optimization of the design, damage tolerance will be incorporated and performance - cost trade-offs considered.

The interesting properties obtained for thermoplastic matrix composites mentioned previously in the exploratory development

program are being evaluated further in two structures programs; both involve the use of graphite-polysulfone. One consists of the fabrication of a main landing gear door for a Convair 200 plane; the other involves the fabrication of a fuselage centerbody for the BQM-34E unmanned drone. Since the matrix is thermoplastic, the structure will be fabricated as a flat panel and then formed into the proper shape for the fuselage. The use of a thermoplastic matrix opens up new possibilities for the fabrication of structures. If these programs are successful, they could have a major impact on the field of composite structures.

The Navy is evaluating the potential use of composite materials in hydrofoils. The main applications would be in the foil and in the strut through which the foil is attached to the hull. Analytical studies have been conducted to determine the composite materials and orientations that would provide the optimum design for each application. An example of the materials considered and their properties are presented in Table IV. The composite structures are designed to meet or exceed the requirements for surface load, bending stiffness, tensile and compressive strength, and deflection of the all-metal components on the existing hydrofoil. The safety factor used for composite components is 1.5 as compared to 1.25 for existing metal components. In addition, the external dimensions of the composite components are to remain the same as for the existing metal design. The relative weights and costs of various materials combinations for the foil are presented in Table V. The very high modulus graphite fibers in the 45° direction provide the required torsional rigidity, and the high strength graphite fibers in the 0° direction provide the needed strength in this direction. A combination of the two provides the maximum weight saving. Boron is not as attractive as graphite because of boron's weight, cost, poorer machinability, and limited bending capability to small radii. A weight and cost comparison of three designs is presented in Table VI. The all-composite design provides the greatest weight savings, accompanied by high cost. However, the 1980 estimate shows lower costs for 100 or more foils for both the composite-steel skeleton design and the all-composite design compared to the all-steel design.

Metal-Matrix Composite R&D in the U.S. Navy

Current Navy research on metal-matrix composites is directed towards the fundamental understanding of structure and its effects on material properties in fiber-reinforced and in situ composites. Exploratory development is concerned with advancing the processing and fabrication methods of candidate composite systems and determining their mechanical properties. At the present time metal-matrix composites are not employed in Navy components, but potential applications are being explored. These separate conveniently into two principal groups: metal-matrix composites for structures in low-

to-moderate temperature environments and metal-matrix composites for high temperature engine use. The former category includes most of the Navy fiber-reinforced composites work; the latter category centers mainly on the in situ (directionally-solidified) eutectic composites with a smaller effort on refractory metal or ceramic filament-reinforced metal-matrix composites.

Fiber-Reinforced Metal-Matrix Composites

The interest of the Navy in fiber-reinforced composites reflects their unique properties; in particular the high specific strength and specific stiffness. Two systems are emphasized in the applications area, titanium matrices reinforced with beryllium fibers and aluminum matrices reinforced with graphite fibers, while the research effort is directed toward examining filament-matrix interface structure and associated effects on mechanical properties, fatigue and toughness behavior, thermal stability, and formability and includes both model and candidate composite systems.

(a) Beryllium-Titanium Composites. The Navy has investigated this composite system over the past six years, directing the effort primarily toward gas-turbine fan and compressor blading in jet engines. By combining beryllium ($E=42 \times 10^6$ psi) with titanium ($E=16 \times 10^6$ psi) the resulting composite represents an improvement over the lower elastic modulus of titanium. In fan blades the increased stiffness permits improved design through the elimination of mechanical bumpers (required to prevent bending of the blades), thereby reducing weight and improving air flow.

In the initial program alternate layers of beryllium wire and titanium sheet were diffusion bonded to form the composite. As the program advanced, beryllium wire was inserted into a titanium tube and extruded into forging preforms for turbine fan blades. Now under examination is beryllium powder and titanium powder inserted into a titanium tube, followed by extrusion. Figure 2 demonstrates these methods of forming the composites. A primary advantage of the powder method is that high cost beryllium wire and titanium foil are avoided resulting in lower cost, \$30-60 per pound, as compared to other metal-matrix composite materials. Recently it has been demonstrated that the extruded preform with the titanium jacket can be forged to a final blade form. This results in a fan blade with beryllium reinforcement in the center and titanium jacket on the outside. At this point several TF41 engine fan blades have been produced by both the wire and powder techniques.

A wide variety of properties are possible in the Be/Ti system depending on the choice of titanium alloy, beryllium alloy, volume fraction reinforcement, and the processing techniques. Table VII provides data showing the variation of properties at ambient temperature for various amounts of beryllium. Of primary interest is the increase in elastic modulus, but falling strength with higher

fraction of beryllium. Table VIII shows that by properly controlling the material variables, composites with high yield strength, or high specific strength, or toughness, etc. can be produced.

The current effort on Be/Ti composites is to fully characterize the effects of processing on structure and mechanical properties. In conjunction with this effort, dynamic and ballistic testing of Be/Ti TF41 fan blades is underway, and initial tests indicate that these blades possess good ballistic impact resistance. The program has demonstrated that Be/Ti composites possess low density, high modulus, good specific strength and impact strength, and can be produced at comparatively low cost.

(b) Aluminum-Graphite Composites. This composite system is under examination because of its potential weight savings advantages in many structural applications for missile and aircraft systems. The Navy supports a development program on Gr/Al aimed at determining the best reinforcing graphite fiber type and matrix aluminum alloy to employ for desired mechanical properties. A competitor to Gr/Al in some applications is Gr/epoxy. But at elevated temperatures in the range of 250-540°C, the Gr/Al composites provide higher strength. A comparison of Gr/Al with other lightweight structural materials, Table IX, shows the potential superiority of Gr/Al composites.

The exploratory effort has advanced to the point where liquid metal infiltration of microfilaments followed by hot pressing is currently the preferred method for producing the Gr/Al composites (as compared to diffusion bonding using large monofilaments or electroplating microfilaments on aluminum followed by hot pressing). Rule-of-mixtures properties were obtained in Thornel 50 fibers/201 matrix aluminum, Figure 3, using this technique. The 201 matrix alloy at this point appears to give composite properties superior to those employing 5056 and 6061 aluminum alloys.

A number of problems must be considered in applying Gr/Al composites, as follows: (1) Development of a reliable, continuous nondestructive inspection method; (2) Production of an acceptable low-cost graphite fiber; (3) Selection of the best matrix alloy for a particular application; (4) Production of a high volume fraction fiber in the composite; (5) Generation of appropriate design data; and (6) Determination of the corrosion behavior of the composite in the marine environment. From a basic viewpoint it is also important to understand the interaction of the graphite fiber surface with the aluminum matrix in both the liquid metal infiltration and hot pressing stages. This could lead to improved fiber coatings, better bonding, and higher transverse strength which is presently only a small fraction of the ultimate strength in the fiber direction.

(c) Fabrication of Metal-Matrix Composites. A research program on deformation of metal-matrix composites relates to both of the above systems. Plastic deformation of composites is being examined using

the model system stainless steel wire-reinforced aluminum. The idea is to simulate the type of forging that a composite material might see when formed to a shape such as a turbine blade.

Recent results in the program have shown that in compression forming with the load perpendicular to the wire reinforcement there is no metal flow in the direction of wire alignment. This plane-strain condition simplifies the elastic-plastic analysis. Two types of damage to the composites result from this forming operation. The more prevalent damage is formation of voids at the fiber-matrix interface; the other is fiber fracture at high strains.

The damage in the composite can be related to the forming pressure ratio q/p , where q is the lateral pressure and p the vertical pressure. By examining q/p and fiber damage, it is possible to set safe limits on the pressure ratio for various reductions, Figure 4. Here curve (a) shows a path leading to fiber failure, curve (c) to void formation, and curve (b) to defect-free forging. Through the slab method of plasticity analysis, this pressure ratio can be calculated for various forging shapes.

High Temperature Metal-Matrix Composites

Navy research on high temperature composites is aimed at the characterization and development of in situ and filament-reinforced metal-matrix composites for blading in turbine engines. The interest in developing materials with higher temperature capability is in improving turbine engine efficiency; this can be translated into improved aircraft range or higher thrust. Navy research and development programs on high temperature composite systems include molybdenum and tungsten wire-reinforced Fe-Cr-Al-Y (to improve creep resistance of this oxidation-resistant alloy); tantalum wire-reinforced silicon nitride (to enhance impact strength); and directionally-solidified ceramic matrix-tantalum fiber composites. Research on structure in the composites is concerned with the growth of structural defects and understanding their effects on mechanical properties, development of rod and lamellar morphology during solidification and the influence of high temperatures on structural stability. Of most interest in the applications area is the exploratory development program on the Ni-Al-Nb eutectic alloy system where the feasibility of making cast, directionally-solidified turbine blades is under examination.

(a) Navy Research on the Ni-Al-Nb In Situ Composite System. This ternary, investigated in the Navy for several years, is one of the most important in situ composites examined to date. Directional lamellae of γ' - δ (Ni_3Al-Ni_3Nb) can be produced under growth conditions which provide plane front solidification. The directional structure possesses extremely high creep strength at elevated temperatures, offering a 50-80°C improvement in turbine inlet temperature over present superalloys. Navy support has aided in the deter-

mination of mechanical properties (tensile strength, modulus, impact strength, creep and rupture) as a function of temperature, understanding of the microstructural effects on creep behavior, and examination of oxidation resistance and protective coatings.

The present program is a step towards eventual application of this system to turbine engine blading. Three investment casting directional-solidification techniques, the modified-Bridgman method, commercial withdrawal, and liquid-metal cooling, are being evaluated to produce a typical blade configuration. In the course of the program lamellar structures have been produced in γ' - δ using both the modified-Bridgman and liquid-metal cooling techniques. The latter creates a higher temperature gradient suppressing constitutional supercooling and is preferred for maintaining the planar growth front needed for producing an aligned structure. In the liquid-metal cooling technique a mold containing liquid eutectic is lowered in vacuum into a molten tin bath. The tin is maintained at a constant level to provide an excellent heat flow path away from the solidifying interface. Both zircon-silica and alumina-silica investment casting mold materials have been employed successfully, but improved mold and core materials are needed for higher temperature use ($> 1650^{\circ}\text{C}$) and improved resistance to chemical attack. The high temperature gradient capability of liquid-metal cooling is desirable for high growth rates; this produces a fine lamellar spacing, which is desired for improved mechanical properties, Figure 5.

The directional solidification of γ' - δ and γ/γ' - δ (Ni-20Nb-6Cr-2.5Al) turbine blades has been explored in the program. The γ/γ' - δ is more difficult to grow under plane front conditions since it requires a G_L/R value of about $150^{\circ}\text{C}\text{-hr}\text{-cm}^{-2}$ as compared to $25^{\circ}\text{C}\text{-hr}\text{-cm}^{-2}$ for γ' - δ , where G_L is the temperature gradient in the liquid at the solid-liquid interface and R is the solidification rate. γ' - δ has been successfully grown in the solid turbine blade configuration with aligned lamellae in the airfoil and cellular structure in the root. The aligned lamellae are needed for high creep resistance in the high temperature area of the airfoil; the cellular structure is preferred for high shear strength and ductility in the lower temperature root. Recently the γ/γ' - δ structure was grown successfully in a cored turbine blade configuration, Figure 6. The cored blade permits the required temperature gradient to be generated.

Present plans are to continue development of the solidification technique emphasizing the γ/γ' - δ system since it is more oxidation resistant and ductile than the γ' - δ structure. Improved temperature gradients and mold materials will be goals.

Concluding Remarks

This paper has not listed every U.S. Navy project involving composite materials. It has attempted to provide the general objectives of the composite materials program, some applications and contributions to composite technology, and a discussion of selected current projects to indicate program directions. The program is carefully planned and coordinated in the Navy through the various stages of research, development and application.

It should be clear that the U.S. Navy recognizes the potential for organic-matrix and metal-matrix composites as structural materials. As more experience is gained through the application of prototype components in actual service environments, greater confidence will be established in designing composites into primary as well as secondary structures. There is little doubt that the use of composites in naval structures will increase dramatically and that an exciting future awaits these materials.

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Table I
Fiber Properties

Candidate Fibers	Strength PSI	Minimum Strength PSI	Modulus MSI	Density Lbs./In ³	Specific Minimum Strength 10 ⁶ In	Specific Modulus 10 ⁶ In
S glass	550,000	450,000	12.3	.090	5.0	137
Graphite	434,000	250,000	31.9	.064	3.9	491
Kevlar	480,000	350,000	20.2	.053	6.6	381

Table II
Properties of Polysulfone-Graphite Laminates - Typical Values

Property	Laminate Configuration			
	0°	±45°	0-90°	90°
Tensile Strength, psi	192,900	20,500	99,600	8,600
Tensile Modulus, MSI	18.7	1.7	8.6	1.0
Compression Strength, psi	151,300	25,200	71,400	---
Compression Modulus, MSI	15.6	2.2	8.9	---
Flexural Strength, psi	214,100	46,400	135,800	---
Flexural Modulus, MSI	13.9	2.2	8.2	---
Interlaminar Shear Str., psi	14,300	---	---	---
Fiber Volume, %	55.3	53.2	55.5	54.1
Specific Gravity, g/cc	1.57	1.51	1.54	1.55

Table III
Comparison of Graphite Fiber/Epoxy Tape and Cloth -
Typical Quasi-Isotropic Laminate (0/90/±45)

		Graphite/ Epoxy Cloth	Graphite/ Epoxy Tape	
Tensile Strength (KSI)	(R/T) (350° F)	68.7 62.6	71.7 62.0	
Tensile Modulus (MSI)	(R/T) (350° F)	8.0 7.5	7.8 7.2	
Design Tensile Strength (KSI)	("B" - Basis) (R/T) (350° F)	61.1 55.1	54.5 48.5	
Compressive Strength (KSI)	(R/T) (350° F)	62.0	65.4	
Compressive Modulus (MSI)	(R/T) (350° F)	7.5	7.0	
Design Compressive Strength (KSI)	("B" - Basis) (R/T) (350° F)	57.5	52.4	
Shear Strength (KSI)	(R/T) (350° F)	9.5 6.6	10.2 6.5	
Design Tensile Strength	Typical C.V. (%)	(R/T) (350° F)	4.0 3.1	6.0-10.0 5.0- 9.0

Table IV
Material Properties Used in Design

Material	Modulus (MSI)				Strength (KSI)				
	E _L	E _T	G _{LT}	ν _{LT}	σ _{tL}	σ _{cL}	σ _{tT}	σ _{cT}	σ _{LT}
Steel	29	29	11	0.33	*	*	*	*	*
S-Glass	8	2.2	0.9	0.26	280	170	11	29	9
Kevlar	11	0.9	0.3	0.30	180	40	5	20	8
Boron	30	2.8	1.0	0.21	180	250	9	30	13
Graphite									
Ultra hi-modulus I	42	0.9	0.7	0.32	170	90	4	20	9
Ultra hi-modulus II	42	0.9	0.7	0.32	90	90	4	20	9
Type II	21	1.3	0.7	0.21	160	160	7	29	10
Low modulus	24	1.3	0.7	0.21	200	200	7	29	13

*The critical steel stress is the yield stress given by the HY number (e.g., 100 for HY 100).

Table V
Weight and Cost Comparison of Materials for Hydrofoil

Material	Thickness (in.)	Layer Direction (deg)	Layer Direction (%)	Weight (lb)	Saving (%)	Cost (\$)	
						1974	1980
Steel							
HY80	0.61	---	---	1,770	---	17,700	23,700
HY100	0.57	---	---	1,670	5.7	16,700	22,400
Boron	1.91	0 and 45	---	1,240	29.9	352,000	173,600
*UHM I	1.62	0 and 45	---	840	52.5	333,000	117,600
*UHM II	2.07	0 and 45	---	1,020	42.4	142,800	102,000
Boron							
*UHM II	1.09	0 45	31.3 68.7	<u>246</u> <u>420</u> 666	62.4	128,600	76,400
*Type II							
*UHM II	1.45	0 45	40.5 59.5	<u>313</u> <u>460</u> <u>773</u>	56.3	113,200	73,300
*LM							
*UHM II	1.28	0 45	37.0 63.0	<u>257</u> <u>438</u> 695	60.7	101,400	66,200
*Type II							
*UHM II	1.25	0 0 45	29.0 7.0 64.0	678	61.7	98,150	65,300
*LM							
*UHM II	1.11	0 0 45	27.0 4.5 68.5	610	65.5	88,000	58,900

*Graphite fibers: LM = Low modulus
Type II = Medium modulus
UHM = Ultra-high modulus

Table VI
1973-74 Cost Comparison for Hydrofoil

Item	Design				
	All-Steel	Composite Skins Steel Skeleton		All-Composite	
		100(A)	10(A)	100(A)	10(A)
Total Weight (lb)	2,719	1,924		1,045	
Weight Saved (lb)	---	795		1,674	
Percent Weight Savings	---	29.2		61.6	
Cost per Foil (\$)					
Materials		18,600	18,600	51,400	51,400
Fabrication ^(C)		25,700	51,400	19,500	39,000
Subtotal		<u>44,300</u>	<u>70,000</u>	<u>70,900</u>	<u>90,400</u>
Tooling and Planning		20,000	171,200	11,300	91,400
Total Cost (\$)	68,000 ^(B)	<u>64,300</u>	<u>241,200</u>	<u>82,200</u>	<u>181,800</u>
Total Cost (\$) 1980 ^(D)	(91,100)	(76,500)	(314,100)	(63,900)	(197,100)

- A. 100 and 10 denote the number of foil ship-sets on which cost is based.
B. Based on cost of \$25/lb for fabricated structure.
C. Based on labor rate of \$20/hr.
D. Cost of labor and steel assumed to increase at 5 percent per year. Cost of materials decreased to \$15,000 for steel skeleton and to \$22,700 for all-composite.

Table VII
Properties of Beryllium—Reinforced Titanium Composites
(Extruded Be and Ti Powder)

Property	Volume % Beryllium			
	20	40	50	60
UTS (KSI)	176	163	140	123
Modulus (MSI)	22.0	26.3	28.6	31.2
Density (lbs/in ³)	0.143	0.123	0.113	0.103
Elongation (%)	10.6	5.3	3.4	2.7
Impact* (ft. lbs.)	18.0	15.0	11.5	7.5

*Standard "V" Notch Test

Table VIII
Be/Ti Material Properties (Typical)

Type	Modulus, Msi	UTS Long, ksi	UTS Transverse Direction, ksi	Yield Strength, ksi	Elongation, %	Charpy, ft-lb	Fatigue Strength* ksi
High Yield Strength	27	120	20	90	2.2	6.5	36
High Yield Strength/ ρ	31	105	15	85	1.6	4.0	38
High Charpy	27	110	20	48	3.6	8.0	36
High Fatigue	31	90	15	48	2.0	4.0	42
High Transverse UTS	27	65	30	48	0.6	4.0	NA

*Fatigue Strength -- Endurance Stress at 10^7 Cycles
Room Temperature
Reverse Bending Test

Table IX
 Specific Strength and Modulus for Graphite/Aluminum and
 Lightweight Metal Alloys

Material	Specific Strength 10 ⁶ In.	Specific Modulus 10 ⁶ In.
Gr/Al (30 V%)	1.4	290
Gr/Al (45 V%)	2.8	550
Ti-6 Al-4 V	1.0	105
Beryllium	0.9	610
7xxx Al Alloy	0.8	100

1. Cavitation Erosion Rate For Various Materials

Be - Ti COMPOSITE FABRICATION STUDY

2. Be-Ti Composite Fabrication Study

COMPARISON OF TEST RESULTS WITH RULE OF MIXTURES (ROM) PREDICTIONS

3. Comparison of Gr/Al Test Results with Rule-of-Mixtures Predictions

4. Limiting Ranges of q/p for Forging Without Damage to Fibers

5. Influence of Solidification Rate and Interlamellar Spacing on Tensile Properties of γ' - δ Eutectic

MICROSTRUCTURE OF CORED $\gamma/\gamma' + \delta$ EUTECTIC TURBINE BLADE

6. Microstructure of Cored $\gamma/\gamma' - \delta$ Eutectic Turbine Blade